

Deliverable 4.1

Report on the Atlantic salmon vaccination strategy for *T. finnmarkense*

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T. FINNMARKENSE

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*T. FINNMARKENSE***Executive Summary**

Tenacibaculosis is a bacterial ulcerative skin disease of many economically important farmed fish species worldwide caused by members of the genus *Tenacibaculum*. In Norwegian aquaculture, the disease caused by the bacterium *Tenacibaculum finnmarkense* leads to significant challenges related to fish welfare, increased mortality, and economic losses. There are currently no available vaccines against tenacibaculosis in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), and the acute course of the disease makes antibiotic treatment ineffective. Therefore, this work aimed to investigate the efficacy of different vaccine regimes with inactivated vaccine against *T. finnmarkense* HJFT in Atlantic salmon. The vaccine was based on formalin inactivated whole cell *T. finnmarkense* formulated with an oil adjuvant for IP vaccination and solubilized in water for immersion vaccination. The vaccine was provided by Vaxxinova (Norway). The antigens were based on priority information from the company (not disclosed).

Four different vaccine regimes, combining oil-based intraperitoneal injection (IP) and water-based immersion (dip), were tested. All vaccination regimes were carried out before initiating smoltification. Immunized smoltified fish were bath challenged with live *T. finnmarkense* HJFT bacteria, at approximately 500 degree-days (DD) after immunization. Two separate infection trials were conducted, with adjustments in bacterial concentration to study disease progression under different conditions. Both infection trials induced tenacibaculosis, characterized by external wounds, high mortality, and histological changes consistent with the disease.

The results demonstrated a specific IgM response against *T. finnmarkense* in all IP vaccinated fish. Significant differences in mortality were observed between unvaccinated control fish and vaccinated fish. Immersion vaccination in combination with IP vaccination gave no additional antibody response, but gave additional protection compared to IP vaccinated fish and unvaccinated fish. This suggests that the elicitation of the mucosal immune system may contribute to the additional protection against *T. finnmarkense*. The immune responses in skin, gills, thymus, nose cavity, and intestine are currently being investigated to determine how immersion vaccination affects the mucosal immunity.

Considering the protection observed with the trial vaccine in this experimental challenge study, the vaccine may become a promising tool to assist the Norwegian salmon aquaculture industry in the combat against tenacibaculosis.

*T. FINNMARKENSE***Contents**

Acronyms and Abbreviations	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Materials and methods	6
2.1. Fish husbandry	6
2.2. Vaccination.....	6
2.3. Sampling.....	8
2.4. Challenge trial	8
2.5. ELISA for detection of specific IgM	10
3. Results and discussion	10
3.1. Growth parameters.....	10
3.2. Specific IgM response	11
3.3. Survival rate after challenge 1 and 2	12
4. Conclusions	15
5. References	16
Document information	17

T. FINNMARKENSE

Acronyms and Abbreviations

CFU	Colony Forming Units
DD	Degree Days
Dip	Immersion
IP	Intraperitoneal
RPS	Relative Survival Rate
TCC	Total Cell Counts

T. FINNMARKENSE

1. Introduction

Tenacibaculosis, also known as non-classical winter ulcer or atypical winter ulcer, has relatively recently emerged as a serious threat to Norwegian farmed salmon. The disease occurs mainly in newly released smolt (Colquhoun, 2022). Outbreaks can also occur later in the production cycle, often in connection with handling and treatment, such as delousing operations (Poppe, 2024). The disease can lead to high mortality, up to 80%, and culling of weakened fish can further increase mortality (Colquhoun, 2022; Poppe, 2024). The disease occurs primarily at low sea temperatures below 7 °C, especially during early spring (March–May) and late autumn (October–December) releases (Veterinærinstituttet, 2021; Åkerblå & Aqua Kompetanse, unpublished). The risk of disease and mortality increases significantly at temperatures below 5°C (Colquhoun, 2022). Outbreaks are usually acute and last for about two weeks, with a rapid increase in mortality in the first week, followed by a gradual decline (Åkerblå & Aqua Kompetanse, unpublished).

Fish affected by tenacibaculosis can be observed in the sea cages with abnormal swimming behavior, often high in the water column, and with visible snout ulcers (Småge, 2018). Clinical findings include characteristic skin and fin lesions, ulceration and tissue necrosis in the skin, head/jaw, and fin areas (Colquhoun, 2022; Poppe, 2024; Småge, 2018). Skin ulcers often have irregular edges, with a zone around the wound edge showing scale loss (Poppe, 2024; Småge, 2018). In severe cases, bony structures in the jaw and skull may be exposed (Colquhoun, 2022). Splitting and erosion of fins, known as fin rot, is also a common symptom of the disease (Poppe, 2024).

Treatment with antibiotics has been shown to be ineffective against tenacibaculosis, especially due to the acute course of the disease (Poppe, 2024). Preventive measures are therefore crucial. As of today, there is no effective vaccine against *Tenacibaculum* spp., but the development of such a vaccine would be an important step in reducing the disease burden (Poppe, 2024). Other preventive measures include ensuring good skin health and smolt quality, as well as minimizing damage to the skin barrier during processing and sea release (Spilsberg et al., 2021). The timing of sea release should be adjusted to avoid low sea temperatures, as this can reduce the risk of outbreaks (Spilsberg et al., 2021). Exposure to low salinities (approximately 26‰) before sea release can also strengthen the fish's resistance against infections (Nylund et al., 2020).

The purpose of this study is to investigate the efficacy of different vaccine regimes, including combinations of dip and IP vaccination with an inactivated *T. finnmarkense* in Atlantic salmon. The goal is to identify the most effective vaccination regime to improve protection against tenacibaculosis.

T. FINNMARKENSE

In the original proposal we included *Tenacibaculum maritimum* vaccination in Atlantic salmon. However, after reviewing all available literature, we revealed that *Tenacibaculum finnmarkense* is the pathogen causing tenacibaculose in Norway, not *T. maritimum*. *T. maritimum* does not cause disease related problems in Norway (Spiltsber et al., 2021) . Due to this fact we decided to include *T. finnmarkense* in our vaccination and challenge experiments

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fish husbandry

Atlantic salmon were provided by the Aquatic and Industrial Laboratory (ILAB) in Bergen (Norway), where the experiment was conducted between September 2024 and January 2025. All fish were confirmed negative for Piscine orthoreovirus, Piscine myocarditis virus, Infectious pancreatic necrosis virus, and Infectious salmon anemia virus. Acclimatization took place 2 weeks before the start of the vaccination trial, and the temperature was gradually adjusted to 12 °C.

At the start of the experiment (T0), fish ($n = 830$, average weight 12 g) were kept in freshwater at 12 °C in a 500 L tank. At vaccination, the vaccinated fish groups were separated from the untreated/control group and were kept in separate 150 L tanks. From the start of the experiment until the intraperitoneal injection (T9), the photoperiod was 12L:12D and then switched to 24L:0D for the rest of the trial. Fish were fed ad libitum with the commercial dry feed Nutra Olympic (Skretting) and were starved 48 h prior to any handling (e.g. transfer, vaccination, tagging). Only fish that appeared healthy were included in the study. Fish displaying deformities, skin ulceration, or other lesions were excluded. During the experiment, all fish showing signs of disease and/or behavioral changes were euthanized. The animal experiments were approved by the Norwegian Food Safety Authority (“Mattilsynet”) (Experiment ID: 27678).

2.2. Vaccination

Four different vaccine regimes, combining IP injection and dip, were tested in Atlantic salmon (Table 1). Two vaccines manufactured by Vaxxinoa (Norway) were used: a dip vaccine and an intraperitoneal injection vaccine, both containing a monovalent *T. finnmarkense genomovar finnmarkense* (VX 1436). The dip vaccine had an antigen dose of 7×10^9 total cell count (TCC)/mL in its final concentration. The IP vaccine (0.05 mL) was used at a dose of 7×10^7 colony forming units (CFU)/dose. For the dip

T. FINNMARKENSE

vaccination, 2 L of vaccine were diluted in 10 L of water in a bucket. Fish were, in small groups, taken from a reservoir tank, dipped in the vaccine solution for 30 s, and transferred to a group-specific tank.

Table 1: Vaccination regimes

Group	Vaccination regime
G1	D1 + D2 + IP – (Dip vaccine x 2 + IP)
G1C	D1 + D2 + IP – (Dip solution without antigen + IP with 0.9% saline)
G2	D1 + IP – (Dip vaccine x 1 + IP)
G3	D1 + IP + DL – (Dip vaccine + IP + late dip (2 days before challenge))
G4	IP
G5	Untreated control

All vaccination regimes were carried out before initiating smoltification (Figure 1). Before IP vaccination, fish were anaesthetized using Finquel vet. 120 mg/L according to SOP Fish anaesthesia and marked with visible implant elastomer (VIE) tagging system. The fish were smoltified for a period lasting six weeks after the final vaccination point (T9). Smoltification was induced by increasing the light regime to 24L:0D. After smoltification, fish were acclimatized to 10 °C over a period of 48 h (2 °C/48 h). Fish were then transferred to the challenge facility (ILAB), and 24 h prior to the challenge, the water parameters were set to 8 °C and 34‰ seawater.

Figure 1: Study timeline. T0 = 0 weeks, first time of vaccination; T3 = 3 weeks post first vaccination; T6 = 6 weeks post first vaccination; T9 = 9 weeks post first vaccination; T15 = 15 weeks post first vaccination.

T. FINNMARKENSE**2.3. Sampling**

Fish were euthanized by an overdose of Finquel vet and sampling was carried out at various time points. Sampling points and the number of fish are summarized in Table 2. Prior to the first dip vaccination (T0), fish ($n = 20$) were sampled and served as controls. Blood was collected from the caudal vein and centrifuged at 1500 g for 10 min for collection of plasma, which was stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Organ tissues, including skin, gills, thymus, nasal cavity, liver, spleen, head kidney, and intestine, were collected and immediately fixed in 10% formalin for histological analysis or in RNA-later (Sigma) for qPCR analysis.

Table 2: Sampling timeline and number of sampled fish. T0 = 0 weeks, first time of vaccination; T3 = 3 weeks post first vaccination; T6 = 6 weeks post first vaccination; T9 = 9 weeks post first vaccination; T15 = 15 weeks post first vaccination.

Gr.	T0	T6	T9			T15	Total
			Day 0	Day 3	Day 7		
1	20	10	10	10	10	20	80
1C		10	10	10	10	10	50
2						20	20
3			10	10	10	20	50
4			10	10	10	20	50
5			10	10	10	20	50
							300

2.4. Challenge trial

The *T. finnmarkense* strain HJFT used in this study was recovered from a tenacibaculosis outbreak in a Northern Norwegian Atlantic salmon farm. The bacteria were grown at $16\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 48 h, and stock solutions were stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The challenge material was produced by inoculating 1 L of Marine Broth, Difco, 2216 (MB) in 2 L Erlenmeyer flasks with 400 μL of frozen bacterial stock solution. These were incubated between 60 and 72 h at $16\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 140 rpm. Bacterial counts were calculated using the most probable number (MPN) method (Blodgett 2010) with 10-fold dilutions in duplicate using 8 replicates per dilution. The average MPN of the duplicates was used to calculate the culture of bacterial concentration, which was then used to calculate the bath concentrations retrospectively.

The fish were challenged by bath in small tanks/buckets holding 60 L sea water that was kept oxygenated (90-100%) using compressed air. Temperature, oxygen levels, and fish behaviour were

T. FINNMARKENSE

monitored during the challenge. The bath challenge period was set to 2 h. Temperature was kept at 8°C throughout the challenge. After 2 h, the fish were returned to the 150 L tanks.

Given the unpredictable nature of *Tenacibaculum* challenge outcomes, the experiment was conducted in two separate sets with adjusted bacterial concentrations. Both challenges were performed with *T. finnmarkense* HJFT (VX1436) (Figure 2). The first challenge was performed in triplicate and included G1, G2, G4, and G5, with 20 fish from each group per tank using a bacterial concentration of 1,7E+06 CFU/ml final volume. Due to the high mortality observed during the first round, the concentration of *T. finnmarkense* in the challenge sample was reduced for the second round to mitigate excessive mortality. The second challenge was performed in triplicate as well and included G1, G2, G3, and G5, with 20 fish from each group per tank, using a bacterial concentration of 1,4E+06 CFU/ml in the challenge volume.

Figure 2: Overview of the number of fish for challenges 1 and 2. Each challenge comprised 3 tanks, each with a total of 80 fish (n = 20 per group), divided into four groups (Groups 1, 2, 4, and 5 for challenge 1 and groups 1, 2, 3, and 5 for challenge 2).

T. FINNMARKENSE

2.5. ELISA for detection of specific IgM

An indirect ELISA was used to determine the specific antibody response (IgM) to *T. finnmarkense* in plasma samples. Ninety-six well microplates (MaxiSorp, Nunc, ThermoFisher Scientific, MA, USA) were pre-treated with poly-Lysine (Sigma-Aldrich, Norway) in carbonate-bicarbonate buffer (C3041, Sigma-Aldrich, Norway) prior to coating to enhance antigen binding. Plates were then washed three times with a PBST solution (PBS, phosphate-buffered saline, pH 7.3, with 0.05% Tween 20) and coated overnight at 4 °C (100 µL/well) with formalin inactivated *T. finnmarkense* at a concentration of 8×10^7 cells/mL. After washing, plates were blocked with 5% dry milk in PBST overnight at 4 °C. Plasma samples, diluted 1:200 in 1% PBST, were added to the wells and incubated overnight at 4°C. After three washes in PBST, mouse anti-trout IgM mAb (IgF1–18 (6–1- 18), 1:1600, 100 µL/well) was added and incubated for 60 min at RT (Hedfors et al., 2012). Following PBST washes, HRP-conjugated goat anti-mouse antibody (Bio-Rad; 1:8000; 100 µL/well) was added and incubated for an additional 60 min at RT. Plates were developed with TMB Chromogen Solution (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA; 100 µL/well), for 30 min at RT in the dark, and the reaction was stopped by the addition of 0.5 M sulfuric acid H₂SO₄ (Sigma-Aldrich, Norway; 50 µL/well). Optical density was measured at 450 nm with a spectrophotometer (VersaMax Absorbance Micro Reader: Molecular Devices, USA). The plasma were additionally tested against *T. ovolyticum* and *T. finnmarkense genomovar ulcerans* using the same ELISA protocol.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Growth parameters

At T0, prior to the first vaccination, 20 fish were sampled and used as control for all vaccine groups. At T15, group 4 had the highest growth in weight gain and SGR, followed by group 5 (untreated control group), while group 1C (control group for group 1) had the lowest growth ($p < 0.0001$) (Figure 3). No significant differences were observed in condition factor between groups, indicating similar overall fish condition throughout the trial (Table 3).

T. FINNMARKENSE

Figure 3: Fish weight (g) for the different vaccination regime groups at T15 (6 weeks post IP vaccination). T0: 0 weeks, first time of vaccination. Different letters represent significant differences between groups.

Table 3: Growth parameters (weight, length, condition factor (K), specific growth rate (SGR)) for the different groups at T15.

	G1 (D1+D2+IP)	G1C (Control)	G2 (D1+IP)	G3 (D1+IP+LD)	G4 (IP)	G5 (control)	
Weight (g)	56.3 ± 8.4	47.2 ± 7.5	54.5 ± 6.8	50.2 ± 6.3	63.2 ± 9.4	60.6 ± 6.8	
Length (cm)	16.8 ± 0.9	15.9 ± 1.1	16.6 ± 0.6	16.4 ± 0.7	17.7 ± 0.8	17.3 ± 0.68	
K-factor	1.2 ± 0.06	1.2 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.05	1.1 ± 0.04	1.15 ± 0.07	1.2 ± 0.07	
SGR (%)		1.4	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.6	1.5

3.2. Specific IgM response

Figure 4 shows the specific antibody response from individual ($n=20$) plasma samples against *T. finnmarkense genemovar finnmarkense*. A specific IgM antibody response was detected in all IP vaccinated groups at 6 weeks post-vaccination (T15), and the responses were significantly ($p < 0.0001$,

T. FINNMARKENSE

Tukey's multiple comparisons test) higher in groups 1, 2, 3, and 4 compared to control groups 1C and 5. There was a variation in response in the vaccine groups between higher and lower responders.

Figure 4: Specific antibody responses in individual ($n = 20$) plasma samples to *T. finnmarkense* genemovar *finnmarkense* at T15. Combination of different letters indicates significant ($p < 0.05$) differences between groups. Error bars indicate a 95 % confidence interval.

In addition, we have tested the cross-reaction with other strains of *Tenacibaculum* spp. We have not found any cross-reaction with *T. ovolyticum*, but specific antibody responses against *T. finnmarkense* genemovar *ulcerans* were detected in IP vaccinated groups in pooled plasma samples ($n=10$) (data not shown).

3.3. Survival rate after challenge 1 and 2

The survival data from challenge 1 show that the control group (group 5) had the highest cumulative mortality, reaching approximately 60% (Figure 5). Among the vaccinated groups, mortality was significantly lower, resulting in relative percent survival (RPS) at the end of the challenge of 36-48%. The survival data from challenge 2 show that the cumulative mortality of the control group (group 5) was approximately 80% (Figure 6). Among the vaccinated groups, mortality was significantly lower, resulting in RPS at the end of the challenge of 34-69%. In fish vaccinated by 2 x dip plus single IP injection (Group 1), the cumulative mortality was approximately 20%, resulting in a vaccine efficacy (RPS) of about 50%. Our experience is that each challenge experiment provides different results. This applies tank-to-tank RPS variation caused by various pathogen loads, fish dynamics, and tank-specific environment. When the difference between tanks in a triplicate challenge experiment is more than 10 percent, it is required to present results from each tank separately. There is a need to repeat the

T. FINNMARKENSE

experiment using a higher number of fish and tanks (replicates) in a semi-commercial scale before any commercialization.

Figure 5: Cumulative mortalities (%) during challenge 1 in Tanks 1 (upper), 2 (middle), and 3 (bottom), including control (G5), D1+IP (G2), IP (G4), and D1+D2+IP (G1).

T. FINNMARKENSE

Figure 6: Cumulative mortalities (%) during challenge 2 in Tanks 4 (upper), 5 (middle) and 6 (bottom) including control (G5), D1+IP (G2), D1+IP+DL (G3) and D1+D2+IP (G1).

Because group composition varies among tanks, infection dynamics will also differ across tanks. This variability can alter the waterborne concentration of, thereby influencing disease transmission, thus mortality.

T. FINNMARKENSE

4. Conclusions

The cumulative mortality in unvaccinated control fish was approximately 60-80% in both challenges, whereas the fish that were vaccinated by 2 x dip plus IP injection of bacterin displayed approximately 20% mortality. All intraperitoneally vaccinated fish exhibited a specific systemic IgM antibody response against *T. finnmarkense*. Combining single immersion vaccination with IP vaccination did not result in any additional antibody response or increased protection compared to IP vaccination alone. In two of three tanks in the second challenge, double immersion with IP vaccination gave additional protection compared to only one immersion with IP vaccination. These results demonstrated that the trial vaccine induced protection against *T. finnmarkense* in an experimental challenge study and suggest that the vaccine has the potential to contribute to improved control of tenacibaculosis in Norwegian salmon aquaculture.

Task 4.6. Synergistic effects of functional feeds and vaccination

Deviation:

The vaccination and challenge experiments for sea bass and salmon are already nearly finished and functional feed developed in WP3 was not included. Any addition of immunostimulatory feed would require a significantly up-scaling of the amount of functional ingredient and the number of experimental fish, which would increase the already expensive vaccine trials several-folds and will not support the 3R principle. The amount of functional ingredient must be in kilogram level, and in a chemical pure form for interpretation. In addition, a pilot trial must be carried out because of feed safety reason since there are no reports on how the vegetable extract may affects fish. For e.g., the *Tenacibaculum* vaccine and challenge trials, there were four different treatment groups. An inclusion of immunostimulatory feed would increase the group number with 2-3x (control feed, diet 1 and diet 2) given two doses of feed ingredients are to be included. This means that task 4.6 will not be carried out.

T. FINNMARKENSE

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